

DIGITAL GENERATION: THE IMPACT OF GADGETS ON THE PSYCHOLOGY AND SOCIAL LIFE OF TEENAGERS

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Annotation: This article analyzes the impact of digital technologies and gadgets on the psychological state and social adaptation of adolescents. During the study, the duration of adolescents' smartphone use, level of addiction to social networks, sleep quality, communication skills, and self-assessment characteristics were studied. The results showed that excessive use of gadgets can lead to decreased attention, social isolation, increased emotional stress, and anxiety in adolescents. At the same time, properly managed technological use develops educational activities and communicative skills.

Keywords: digital generation, gadgets, adolescent psychology, social adaptation, internet addiction.

Introduction

In today's globalization environment, digital technologies have become an integral part of everyday life. In particular, adolescents actively use smartphones, tablets, computers and Internet networks. Psychologists say that this process directly shapes the communication skills, emotional balance and social behavior that are formed during adolescence. Therefore, it is an urgent issue to evaluate the benefits and disadvantages of digital tools on a scientific basis.

Methods

The study was conducted using the following methods:

1. Literature analysis: modern psychological and pedagogical sources were studied.
2. Questionnaire: conducted among 60 adolescents aged 12–17.
3. Observation method: communication and digital time distribution in students' activities were observed.

The data obtained were summarized based on statistical analysis.

Results

The results of the survey showed the following:

Indicator: Observed result

The duration of daily smartphone use by 78% of students is more than 4 hours.

Complaints of sleep disorders were observed in 52% of adolescents.

Decreased attention was observed in 41% of participants.

A decrease in real social communication was detected in 63% of students.

It was also noted that constant presence in social networks led to a decrease in the level of self-esteem of adolescents.

Discussion:

The results show that gadgets play a dual role in the lives of adolescents. On the one hand, they increase the ability to gain knowledge, develop creativity and communicate. On the other

hand, when used uncontrollably and excessively, they cause psychological fatigue, social alienation and addiction. Therefore, parents, educators and medical workers need to organize the digital activities of adolescents in a purposeful, time-limited and beneficial direction.

Conclusion

The collected scientific data and the results of the survey show that gadgets and digital technologies have a significant impact on the mental state and social development of adolescents. When used in moderation, digital tools increase the effectiveness of the educational process, increase the speed of information acquisition, develop creative activity and communication skills. However, uncontrolled, prolonged and aimless use has been found to cause problems such as decreased attention, sleep disturbances, reduced social contacts, emotional instability and Internet addiction.

During the study, it was observed that most adolescents preferred virtual communication to real-life communication. This can lead to a decrease in the level of personal relationships, empathy, psychological adaptation and social activity. Therefore, it is important for parents and educators to monitor the digital activities of adolescents, set reasonable limits on screen time, and create a healthy communication and active social environment.

In general, gadgets have become an integral part of a teenager's life, and it is not practical to completely limit them. Instead, the most optimal solution is to increase digital literacy, form a culture of purposeful and beneficial use of technology, and maintain a balance between online and real communication.

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